

FDO Bulletin 2024-1 June 2024

FDOF Work after the Berlin Implementation Summit

Become engaged in the FDOF work

Berlin FDO Summit, Washington FDO Conference and Beyond

Preparing the Berlin Implementation Summit was an intensive phase of work for the FDO Forum which is based on voluntary engagement. While the Leiden FDO Conference was determined by finishing the basic specifications and plans to implement FDOs, the Berlin Summit showed that there are already many groups implementing FDO-based solutions. The fact that different flavours were presented indicated the need to focus on increased interoperability. This will be addressed in the 3rd FDO conference which will take place in Washington DC in 2025. The interest of the FDOF in engaging other regions is expressed by supporting the idea to have the FDO conference 2026 on the African continent. ***The Summit summary from the FDO Forum (FDOF) is attached to this document and will also be added to the website. All recordings and material of the summit and the training courses have been uploaded to the summit website (<https://fairdo.org/fdof-summit-2024/>).***

Engagement and Collaborations

On the one hand the summit showed that the expectations with respect to the FDOF are increasing, on the other hand the FDOF remains an initiative with voluntary participation and thus limited capabilities. Therefore, we are dependent on the engagement of the experts who are working in projects related to FDOs as in-kind contributions. This, however, will not be sufficient especially to meet the policy related expectations. The FDOF will therefore look for strategic collaboration agreements with initiatives and organisations with mutual interests. A first CA has been signed already with DIN to push the transformation of the FDO specifications into ISO standards, a second CA with the FDO One project is in preparation to jointly establish an international FDO testbed, a third CA should be prepared to jointly generate FDO Compliance Profiles (see below) and an intensification of the interaction with RDA FDOFIG has been agreed upon.

Get engaged with the concrete FDOF activities and suggest collaborations by sending an email to peter.wittenburg@mpi.nl.

FDO Forum Lightweight Governance

The FDOF changed character during the last year towards focussing on FDO specifications and stimulating/coordinating implementations which also implicated that some of the early members of the Steering Committee are not active anymore. After 3 years of working hard in establishing a fundament we decided to establish a lightweight governance to increase the efficiency and transparency of the processes and to adjust SC membership to the new challenges. The lightweight governance document can be seen here. We are now in the process of (1) installing a nomination committee to initiate the process and (2) setting up an International Advisory Board.

All FDO community members have the possibility to suggest candidates that fulfil the criteria for SC and IAB membership. We will send separate emails to the community with more details.

FDOF Workshops & Lectures

Due to the preparations of the Berlin Summit we postponed the work on workshops and lectures, but we are working on new items. **First workshops** which we want to organise together with industry experts will be on the “layered nature of the Global Integrated Dataspace (GIDS)”. Many digital artifacts will be open and require simple means to participate. However, many will be subject of protection like

medical or industrial data. Therefore, the GIDS needs to be constructed by using a simple technology such as FDOs as the bottom interoperability layer, which then forms a common dataspace. On top of this FDO layer there will emerge all kinds of data spaces that apply technologies such as the Eclipse Data Connector (EDC) to control the use of data. These technologies are more complex, demanding some form of centralism, etc. In the FDO One Project the interaction between the FDO and

the EDC layer is being tested with the help of a suitable use case. In workshops after the summer break we will demonstrate and discuss the pros and cons of these different solutions and the usefulness of their integration. **Other workshops** will focus on the clarifications about the “FDO Flavours” which is a topic FDO TSIG is focusing on currently. These are planned for September/October.

We will inform you early enough about our plans via the website and by email. Suggestions from the FDO Community are also welcome, please, send suggestions to secretariat@fairdo.org.

FDO Training

At the Summit the demand for basic and advanced training was so extreme that we decided to respond to the request by repeating the basic training as soon as possible. Due to the workload and the vacation period this training will probably be organised in September. In parallel, a collaboration between RDA FDOFIG and FDOF started to work out a more comprehensive and structured training program. Presentations and discussions of concrete implementations will also be invited.

We will inform you about the training events which will be organised as online events via the website and by emails. Suggestions from the FDO Community are also welcome, please, send suggestions to secretariat@fairdo.org.

FDO Implementation Variants

At the summit 28 presentations about concrete FDO work were given and they were selected from double as much very good submissions. These presentations showed that (1) the concept of FDOs is broadly taken up already, (2) FDOs evolve in an existing landscape of related approaches, and (3) in some cases the term FDO is used without knowing about the FDO specifications. The FDOF is intensifying the discussions and clarifications around these implementation variants in the TSIG working group with the help of two papers: (1) A comparison of different approaches which is understandable for lay-persons and (2) a deep technical paper which is driven by procedural decisions. Both papers should be ready as first versions in September. The discussions about FDO Flavours indicated that several experts were not aware about the semi-formal FDO Requirements Specifications which can be found here: [FDO Forum FDO Requirement Specifications \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/record/1000000)

Interested experts are welcome to participate in these elaborations – just send an email to one of the TSIG co-chairs: Christophe.blanchi@dona.net, anders@dkrz.de, peter.wittenburg@mpi.nl

FDO and Operations

An increasing number of implementations is addressing the question of how to relate operations with FDOs. The FDO TSIG working group started a new subgroup focussing on working out models for this relation where two major issues are currently being addressed: (1) How to do FDO-Operation Linking by using “FDO Types” and (2) how to design “active objects” that act autonomously. An important aspect will always be of how to control usage of specific data by restricting the set of allowed operations. A first orientation meeting took place and further meetings are planned to also discuss concrete implementations. The intention is to work on real papers that elaborate on specific issues.

Everyone who is working on this topic is invited to participate in this TSIG subgroup. In case of interest, please, send an email to nicolas.blumenroehr@kit.edu.

FDO One Project

As we have seen during the FDO Implementation Summit, an increasing number of projects is turning the concept of FDOs into practical solutions. Mostly these projects are vertically organised starting from a scientific application or interest and having a multitude of such projects is very important. The FDO One project has a clear horizontal motivation, i.e. it focuses on providing a basic infrastructure for FDOs, on kicking off an international FDO testbed, working out the layered structure for GIDS (see above) and starting the standardisation roadmap process together with DIN. FDO One is strictly committed to follow the official FDO Specifications. This horizontal approach is the reason why we want to mention this project in this bulletin. Currently, FDO One is working on a collaboration agreement to ensure a close interaction with the FDOF, since having a basic showcase infrastructure, developing the international FDO testbed and testing out the interfacing with industry standards such as I4.0 Asset Administration Shell and IDSA Eclipse Data Connector is of greatest relevance for FDOF. It should be noted that other showcase infrastructures based on other technologies can be developed. The only criterion is compliance with the FDO Specifications.

An overview can be seen here, code will be made available via GitHub and a website (<http://fdo-one.org>) will come soon. Questions can be directed to Philipp.wieder@gwdg.de.

FDO Compliance Profiles

At the FDO Summit Erik Schultes presented his idea of FDO Compliance Profiles which was well perceived and also supported by the FDOF. The idea is that all “flavours” that claim to be compliant with the FDO Specifications fill in a web-form with checkboxes which then indicates the level of compliance. First interactions resulted in the following process: (1) With the help of a few Guinea Pig projects the web-form will be tested and optimised. (2) If this has been done, every project or initiative is welcome to test its compliance. All submitted forms will be evaluated by experts from GO-FAIR and FDOF based on a collaboration agreement.

We will inform everyone when the webform has been tested and make a statement at the website.

FDO Specifications

Several times we have referred to the FDO specifications. We should mention them here again. All official documents can be found here: <https://fairdo.org/specifications/>. We distinguish between core documents and documents that work out specific details. The core documents include an “FDO Overview” which explains the relevance of the various documents, the “FDO Requirements Specifications” which are THE BASIC Standard and the “Implementation of Attributes, Types, Profiles and Registries” document which required many discussions to achieve agreements. While the first two documents are in a Proposed Recommendation state, the last document is still a Working Document. We just decided to move the last document ahead after having clarified the last questions. All last versions have been and will be uploaded to Zenodo. An overview about the documents can be seen here: [Specifications | FAIR Digital Objects Forum \(fairdo.org\)](#)

A new document has been finalised which summarises the specifications for data FDOs which are those FDO configurations which include some bit-sequences. It does not replace the full specification document, but it is much easier to read. The FDO-D document can be found here (<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1gAJQ-qhMH7iEJwEDeCBTnn9pxjOKdtNF/view?usp=sharing>) and will be uploaded to Zenodo as soon as possible.

Responsible for this FDO Bulletin are the FDO-SC Co-Chairs:

Christine Kirkpatrick, Dimitris Koureas, George Strawn, Peter Wittenburg

Comments/question can be sent to secretariat@fairdo.org

FDO Implementation Summit 2024

Looking Back

Christine Kirkpatrick, Dimitris Koureas, George Strawn, Peter Wittenburg

This was the second conference with the focus on FAIR Digital Objects organised by the FDO Forum. The Leiden meeting in 2022 was special in so far that everything was new and many participants had not heard about FDO details beforehand. The working groups wanted to have their sessions to finalise their basic specification work which some newcomers found difficult to follow. In Leiden we heard a lot about the promises of FDOs and the thoughts about which role FDOs could play when developing the global integrated dataspace. During the Berlin meeting we could get an impression on the many ongoing implementation steps towards reality.

The meeting started with a training day where experts were asked to present basics about FDOs as well as about some advanced work. These sessions were a success for two reasons: (1) After the first 40 summit registrations all places were booked showing the great interest in getting concrete information about FDO related work. (2) The amount of interactions during the sessions created an excellent atmosphere. One of the lessons learned from the Leiden meeting was to organise a newcomer session. Sara elGebali and Anne Fouilloux managed to also create a great atmosphere where small groups were asked to interact about open questions. A few FDO experts were invited to answer questions, but were not allowed to intervene at the beginning. The top floor of the DIN building which allowed the participants to look across the roofs of Berlin completed the positive impressions.

During the summit a remarkable number of concrete contributions were presented which were selected from twice as many very good submissions. Altogether, these submissions showed that FDOs are reality and are already being implemented in a variety of labs along two dimensions: most are working on vertical scientific applications, but some are also addressing horizontal core FDO technologies to drive infrastructure building. A highlight was certainly the presentation of the lightning talks where colleagues managed to present major messages within three minutes.

The presentations showed that there are different “flavours” of FDO implementations raising a few questions: (1) Are these flavours all compliant with the FDO specifications as defined by the FDO Forum? (2) Does everyone agree on basic principles such as machine actionability, suitable level of abstraction, importance of typing, etc.? One major distinction between implementations can be described by the terms “webby” and “non-webby”, i.e. some fully rely on the URL/HTTP/HTML technology stack, while others rely on Handles/DOIs and structured information. Most differences can be found in packaging the semantics used in the structure resulting from the resolutions of either the URLs (landing page), the Handles (attribute-value structures) or even in complex metadata schemas as developed in some scientific or industrial domains. These differences confirm the FDOF view that only minimal mandatory specifications should be made mandatory by the FDOF. It is obvious that the further development needs to be based on clear specifications, but on the other hand shows enough flexibility to allow for different implementations. There was evidence that some colleagues were even not aware that there are FDO specifications and that many implementations are being developed in separation. But there is also an indication of coalescence driven by the insights due to all these concrete implementations. While until now most FDO work is being done embedded in projects, it is welcomed that in the FDO One project the FDO is the core focus, developing a basic infrastructure, initiating an international FDO testbed, working on bridge-building with other dataspace that rely on industrial type of technologies. There is some optimism that FDO One may be kicking-off a standardisation process.

Of great value were also the three panels with distinguished experts. From the “Essential Factors for enabling FDOs” panel FDOF can draw the following conclusions: (1) need to increase the measures for international capacity building and education, (2) strengthen the community engagement, (3) enhance interoperability and use open standards where possible, (4) promote policy advocacy, and (5) ensure equity and inclusion, i.e. addressing in particular the international dimension. For an organisation which is based on voluntary work this is a tall order. FDOF needs to work out how efforts can be intensified.

From the panel on “FDO Forum Future” one can also draw a few essentials: (1) FDOF efforts should be embedded in current trans-regional developments and interdisciplinary efforts; (2) FDOF needs to understand that the expectations towards the FDO and FDOF are growing due to new initiatives such as “dataspaces” and already ongoing international interactions; (3) There is an urgent need for transcontinental solutions as a result of fair interactions and by including a broad number of stakeholders; (4) The work on demonstrable use cases across borders which act as catalysts should be increased; (5) There is a clear need to work on the clarification of terminology to increase the common understanding.

From the panel on “FDO Flavours” we can also draw some essentials: (1) The discussion on flavours is necessary, but we need to accept that there are multiple ways to implement FDOs and wishes to accommodate specialty needs. Most of these needs will become apparent through ongoing use cases meeting specific purposes and demonstrating a few typical patterns; (2) A major difference can be found in “webby” and “non-webby” approaches and the ways metadata is packaged into attributes of different structures (Handle Records, Landing Pages, Metadata frameworks). Hybrid solutions should be possible; (3) A major question then is how to achieve interoperability. Looking at layers could be a promising approach and the challenge of a suitable FDO typing framework needs to be addressed. Interoperability requires a proper design; (4) Whatever FDOF will be doing, it needs to follow a pragmatic approach that is made up of connectors, protocols, or gateways

A few important actions can be drawn from these discussions:

- FDOF needs to take actions to disseminate the specifications, to check them against practices and to bring developers together.
- More analysis work needs to be carried out by the TSIG working group to analyse and compare the different flavours and tackle the typing and interoperability issue.
- Erik Schultes presented the idea of FDO Compliance Forms, which could be used for the self-assessment of candidate FDO technology, was very well received and will be worked out.
- Finally, FDOF needs to address the international dimension.

The well-known acronym FAIR can also be interpreted as data that are Fully AI Ready. During the walking dinner and social event at Berlin’s famous Museum für Naturkunde, a dialogue was hosted under the Brachiosaurus on the topic “FDOs and AI”. Aarne Talman, Data & AI Senior Manager at Accenture and Large Language Model expert fielded questions and elaborated on numerous cross-cutting issues: The role of FDOs in ensuring equitable data access for training LLMs; The role of FDOs and rich provenance to give credit, to assess bias or errors in AI output; Are ML applications FDOs? Should they be? How will the FDO spec impact the future developments of AI? The dialogue was informal but well attended by Summit participants.

Summarising we can state that the Berlin summit

- indeed focussed on implementations and showed that the concept of FDOs is taking off,
- was very productive in so far that from the beginning lots of discussions and interactions took place which stimulated dialogues and work beyond the conference
- clearly identified the next steps for the FDO Forum.

Therefore it was a logical follow up that the focus of the 3rd FDO conference, which will probably happen at the AGU facilities in Washington DC in 2025, will be put on the interoperability issues. There is an interest from our African colleagues to organise the FDO conference 2026 in an African country. We as co-chairs support this idea and suggest taking measures to prepare for such a step.

As the FDO Forum we need to find ways to intensify the engagement to meet the expectations. We already took steps to implement a lightweight governance structure that will help to make our decision processes more transparent and open. This implies that we will also increase some light formalisms to understand who is a member of the FDO Forum and thus part of the decision-making processes. Currently, the FDO Forum only manages a list of registered individuals which are part of the “FDO community”. FDOF also needs to review its working group activities and make suggestions to tackle the challenges.

We welcome the idea to ask all presenters and all who submitted abstracts for extended paper publications using the TIB Open publishing possibility.

As co-chairs of the FDOF we would like to thank all those colleagues who contributed to the success of this FDO Implementation Summit: the summit steering and program committees, the local organising committee, the presenters, the panellists, the session and panel chairs. We also would like to thank the FDO One project and COS for its funding support and DIN and MfN/Leibniz for offering their facilities.

All recordings and material about the Summit sessions and the training courses are accessible via the Summit website (<https://fairdo.org/fdof-summit-2024/>).